

Urban and Rural Population Pyramids in Georgia Since 1950s

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Abstract—In the years followed independence, an economic crisis and some conflicts led to the displacement of many people inside Georgia. The growing poverty, unemployment, low income and its unequal distribution limited access to basic social service have had a clear direct impact on Georgian population dynamics and its age-sex structure. Factors influencing the changing population age structure and urbanization include mortality, fertility, migration and expansion of urban. In this paper presents the main factors of changing the distribution by urban and rural areas. How different are the urban and rural age and sex structures? Does Georgia have the same age-sex structure among their urban and rural populations since 1950s?

Keywords—Age and sex structure of population, Georgia, migration, urban-rural population.

I. INTRODUCTION

DEVELOPING countries have rapidly urbanized since 1950. To explain urbanization, standard models have emphasized rural-urban migration, focusing on rural push factors (agricultural modernization and rural poverty) and urban pull factors (industrialization and urban-biased policies). Some developing countries' rapid urban growth and urbanization can also be linked to demographic factors, i.e. rapid internal urban population growth, or an urban push. The much lower urban mortality of today's developing countries, relative to Industrial Europe, where higher urban death rates virtually offset urban births, has compounded the effects of migration. High urban natural increase, rather than migration, is also found to be associated with urban congestion, thus providing further insight into the phenomenon of urbanization without growth [1].

Population of Georgia decrease since 1990's. Population of Georgia was 3.5 million in 1950 according National Statistics Office of Georgian (Geostat) and it reached highest level at the end of the 1980's, population census conducted in 1989 shows that population was 5.4 million. Latest population census conducted in the country shows that population of Georgia in 2014 is 3.7 million [2].

In the period from 1950 to 1990 the main component of population formation was natural increase (see Fig. 2) and out-migration was insignificant indicator [4]. Population of Georgia has decreased since 1990's and main impact of population decline related to emigration (see Fig. 3), [6].

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Fig. 1 Population trend of Georgia since 1950

Fig. 2 Trends of crude death and birth rates and natural increase rate in Georgia since 1950

Fig. 3 Migration trends since 1960

In the years followed independence of Georgia, an economic crisis and some armed conflicts led to the displacement of many people. The growing poverty, unemployment, low income and its unequal distribution limited access to basic social service have had a clear direct impact on Georgian population dynamics and its age-sex structure.

Fig. 4 Population pyramid of Georgia in 1950

Fig. 5 Population pyramid of Georgia in 2015

Population pyramid of Georgia in 1950's has a sharply progressive face, where population was young, but in 2015, the population of Georgia faces challenges of depopulation and ageing. According to UN estimates median age of population Georgia in 1950 was 27.3 and in 2015 is 38.1 and it projected to continue increase [4].

The next factor of changing population dynamics and age-sex structure related to industrialization for the period from 1950 to 1980. In Georgia the growing industrialization and construction which can be related to various changes in demographic and migration characteristics of the population. The terms industrialization and modernization have directly or indirectly responsible for changes which have occurred in the age-sex structure and other socio-economic composition of the population. Industrialization became additional push factor for young people to migrate from rural to urban areas. Consequence of this urbanization should be negative effect of population dynamics Georgia had faced more aged population in rural than in urban areas.

The next very important issue in deference between urban-rural population age and sex structure is due to territories being in fact out of control of governments of Georgia. Since 1993-1994 Abkhazia and a large part of South Ossetia and since 2008 the whole South Ossetia have been out of control of Georgian government. Since the conflicts of the 1990s and 2008 August War, Georgia has experienced a high influx of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs). Conflicts in Abkhazia and South Ossetia during the 1990s have caused around 236,000 people to become internally displaced. Later, due to the 2008 August War, 17,000 people had to flee from their homes. Moreover, there are "3,000 people who have been

displaced more than once. Results population census 2002 shows that 73% IDP's live in urban areas.

All the above mentioned, first of all it is important to answer the following questions: Does Georgia have same age-sex structure among their urban and rural populations? How different are the urban and rural age and sex structures? Next step for our research will be explore and discussing the factors and qualitative aspects of population age-sex structure dynamics by urban and rural. For our research we are going to use several data sources: (1) Official data which provided by National Statistical Office of Georgia [2]; (2) Data from population census conducted in Georgia since 1959; (3) UN estimates [3].

II. URBAN AND RURAL POPULATION IN GEORGIA

Preliminary results of census held in November, 2014 show Georgia's population at 3,729,635, which is 14.7% decline compared to 2002 when the previous census was carried out and when the figure stood at 4.37 million. 57.38% of population lives in urban areas and 42.6% of population lives in rural areas. The largest city is capital city Tbilisi (with 1,118,035 people). According to population census 2002, 2.1 million lives in rural area, which is 13.4% decline compared to 1989 [5]. This decrease of rural population is related to some territories is out of control of Georgian Government. Soon after independence, Georgia had to face two conflicts, which resulted into a loss of control by the Georgian government over most of Abkhazia and a large part of South Ossetia (Table I). However, most important factors are related to low fertility, high mortality and high migration from rural to urban areas. According these two population censuses (1989 and 2002), share of men in rural areas is 48.6%, which is related to lower life expectancy at birth but main determinant is inter-migration where male population goes to the big cities for a job.

Fig. 6 Share and annual rate of change of urban population in Georgia

Share of urban population of all population increasing rapidly since 1950. At the same time annual change rate seems stable for the same period, but rapid change observed only recent period. This change should be explained by change of territorial boundary of some cities, like Tbilisi and Batumi.

According to population census 1959, Population of Georgia is young. There is a different between urban and rural age pyramids. More people are living in rural areas.

In 2002, situation changed dramatically, more people live in urban areas. But after age 60, more people lives in rural. Population of Georgia is aged and in rural areas is more than in urban.

Fig. 7 Urban-Rural population pyramid in Georgia according to population census 1959

Fig. 8 Urban-Rural population pyramid in Georgia according to population census 2002

As already been mentioned, Tbilisi is the biggest city in terms of number of population. In 1959 Tbilisi's population was 0.69 million and in 2002 it is almost twice larger – 1.08 million.

Fig. 9 Population pyramid in Tbilisi according to population censuses 1959 and 2002

III. CONCLUSION

In Georgia more people lives urban than in rural and urbanization process going very rapidly.

Population pyramid is very difference between rural and urban and especially in Tbilisi where live around 30% of

Georgian population.

First and most significant factor of change population age-sex structure by urban and rural is international migration. Next factor related to displacement many people due to conflicts.

The next step to our research is to analyze data of latest population census conducted in 2014. The final results will be available spring of 2016.

APPENDIX

TABLE I
POPULATION BY REGIONS ACCORDING TO POPULATION CENSUS 1989 AND 2002 IN GEORGIA

Regions	1989	2002
Georgia	5400841	4371,535
Urban	2991352	2284796
Rural	2409489	2086739
Tbilisi	1246936	1081679
Urban	1246814	1081532
Rural	122	147
Autonomous Republic of Abkhazia	525061	1956
Urban	247543	...
Rural	277518	1956
Autonomous Republic of Adjara	392432	376016
Urban	181289	166398
Rural	211143	209618
The South Ossetian Autonomous Oblast	98527	...
Urban	49453	...
Rural	49074	...
Guria	158053	143357
Urban	45202	37531
Rural	112851	105,826
Imereti	766892	699666
Urban	409178	323792
Rural	357714	375874
Kakheti	441045	407182
Urban	100138	84827
Rural	340907	322355
Mtskheta - Mtianeti	121791	125443
Urban	35360	32144
Rural	86431	93299
Racha - Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti	59757	50969
Urban	12573	9587
Rural	47184	41382
Samegrelo - Zemo Svaneti	424746	466100
Urban	170737	183133
Rural	254009	282967
Samtskhe-Javakheti	235512	207598
Urban	86169	65535
Rural	149343	142063
Kvemo Kartli	608491	497530
Urban	271019	186505
Rural	337472	311025
Shida Kartli	321598	314039
Urban	135877	113812
Rural	185721	200227

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